

Supplementary material 1. Original Survey instrument (Spanish version)

Sección 1. Características Sociodemográficas (6 ítems)

1. Edad (años):

Respuesta numérica (en años)

2. Sexo:

Masculino

Femenino

3. Lugar de origen:

Managua

Carazo

León

RAAS

Matagalpa

Chinandega

Granada

Rivas

Masaya

RAAN

Chontales

Boaco

Prefiero no decirlo

Nota: Los participantes indicaron municipio/departamento de forma abierta; se estandarizó a nivel departamental.

4. Año de la carrera de Medicina:

1er año

2do año

- 3er año
- 4to año
- 5to año
- 6to año

5. Fototipo según Fitzpatrick :

Figura Suplementaria 1. Escala de referencia visual para los seis fototipos cutáneos de Fitzpatrick

Figura Suplementaria 1. Escala de referencia visual para los seis fototipos cutáneos de Fitzpatrick. Esta figura ilustra los seis fototipos cutáneos de Fitzpatrick (I–VI), que abarcan desde piel muy clara hasta piel profundamente pigmentada, y fue desarrollada específicamente como una ayuda visual dentro del cuestionario del estudio para facilitar la autoidentificación y clasificación precisa por parte de los estudiantes. La imagen fue generada sintéticamente mediante un modelo de Inteligencia Artificial (IA) y posteriormente evaluada y validada por un dermatólogo certificado, con el fin de garantizar la exactitud clínica y la integridad científica, confirmando que cada representación se alinea con las características funcionales y fenotípicas de la escala de Fitzpatrick. Asimismo, al tratarse de una obra generada por IA, esta imagen no está sujeta a derechos de autor tradicionales y es de libre uso para fines públicos, académicos y profesionales.

- Tipo I
- Tipo II
- Tipo III
- Tipo IV
- Tipo V
- Tipo VI
- No sé

6. ¿Cómo describirías tu tipo de piel?

- Grasa
- Seca
- Mixta
- Normal
- Sensible
- No sé

Sección 2. Conocimientos sobre Fotoprotección (7 ítems)

7. ¿Sabes qué es un protector solar?

- Sí
- No estoy seguro
- No

(0=No, 0.5=No estoy seguro, 1=Sí)

8. ¿Sabes qué significa la fotoprotección?

- Sí
- No

(0=No, 1=Sí)

9. ¿Conoces el FPS mínimo recomendado para uso diario?

- Sí

No estoy seguro

No

(0=No, 0.5=No estoy seguro, 1=Sí)

10. ¿Cuál protector solar consideras bueno?

Respuesta abierta

(1 punto si se menciona al menos uno válido, 0 si “No sé” o en blanco)

11. ¿Sabes que algunos protectores solares dañan ecosistemas marinos?

Sí

No

(0=No, 1=Sí)

12. ¿Conoces los fotoprotectores endógenos (p.ej., melanina)?

Sí

No

(0=No, 1=Sí)

Sección 3. Actitudes hacia la Fotoprotección (6 ítems)

13. ¿Consideras que tienes suficiente información sobre riesgos de la sobreexposición solar?

Sí

Limitada

No

(0=No, 1=Limitada, 2=Sí; luego normalizado 0-1))

14. ¿Con qué frecuencia lees los componentes de protectores solares?

Nunca

A veces

Siempre

(0=Nunca, 1=A veces, 2=Siempre; luego normalizado 0-1))

15. ¿Con qué frecuencia verificas el FPS antes de usar protector solar?

- Nunca
- Rara vez
- Frecuentemente
- Siempre

(0=Nunca, 1=Rara vez, 2=Frecuentemente, 3=Siempre; luego normalizado 0-1))

16. ¿Cuál es tu principal motivación para usar protector solar?

- Prevención de cáncer de piel
- Prevención de fotoenvejecimiento
- Motivación combinada
- Evitar quemaduras solares
- Extender tiempo de exposición de forma segura
- Experiencia previa de daño solar

(Prevención de cáncer=2, motivación combinada=1, extender tiempo=0, otros=1; luego normalizado 0-1))

17. ¿Cual es el principal Factor que consideras (independientemente del FPS) al elegir un protector solar?

- Precio
- Ingredientes naturales
- Textura
- Marca
- Todos los anteriores
- No se

(ingredientes naturales=1, Textura= 1, Marca=0, Precio=0, todas las anteriores=1)

18. ¿Cuál es tu formulación preferida de protector solar?

- Crema

- Gel
- Spray
- Otro
- Indiferente

(1 punto cualquier respuesta menos “Indiferente”, 0 si “Indiferente”)

Sección 4. Prácticas de Fotoprotección (7 ítems)

19. ¿Usas protector solar?

- Nunca
- A veces
- Siempre

(0=Nunca, 1=A veces, 2=Siempre; luego normalizado 0-1))

20. ¿Que tan usual es que te apliques protector solar durante actividades al aire libre?

- Nunca
- Rara vez
- Frecuentemente
- Siempre

(Codificado: 0=Nunca, 1=Rara vez, 2=Frecuentemente, 3=Siempre, luego normalizado 0-1)

21. ¿A que edad iniciaste a usar protector solar?

- Respuesta numérica
- Nunca he usado

(Codificado: 0=Nunca, 1=>25 años, 2=18-25, 3=11-17, 4=5-10, 5=<5 años; luego normalizado 0-1)

22. ¿Tu familia usa protector solar regularmente?

- Sí, regularmente
- Ocasionalmente/no consistente

No

(Sí=2, Ocasional=1, No=0; luego normalizado 0-1)

23. ¿Usas otras medidas de protección solar además del protector?

Ninguna

Al menos una (sombrero, ropa, sombra)

Todas las anteriores

(Todas=2, al menos una=1, ninguna=0; luego normalizado 0-1)

24. Como estudiante de medicina, ¿recomiendas protector solar a familiares, amigos o pacientes?

Nunca

A veces

Siempre

(Nunca=0, A veces=1, Siempre=2; luego normalizado 0-1)

25. ¿Qué FPS sueles usar normalmente?

Menor de 30 o no uso

30 o más

(Menor de 30=0, 30 o más=1)

Sección 5. Barreras para implementación de practicas adecuadas de fotoproteccion (2 ítems)

26. ¿Cuál es tu principal razon de no adherencia al uso de protector solar o fotoprotección?

Olvido

Incomodidad

Falta de conocimiento sobre frecuencia de aplicación

Otro

(Descriptivo, no puntuado)

27. ¿Qué te ayudaría a usar protector solar o fotoprotección más regularmente?

- Recordatorios (apps/mensajes)
- Mayor accesibilidad económica
- Formulaciones más convenientes
- Más información sobre riesgos solares
- Más campañas educativas en redes sociales
- Otro

(Descriptivo, no puntuado)

Supplementary Material 2. Translated Survey Instrument (English Version)

Section 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics (6 items)

1. Age (years):

Numeric response (in years)

2. Sex:

Male

Female

3. Place of origin:

Managua

Carazo

León

RAAS

Matagalpa

Chinandega

Granada

Rivas

Masaya

RAAN

Chontales

Boaco

Prefer not to say

Note: Participants indicated municipality/department in an open-ended format; responses were standardized at the departmental level.

4. Year of medical school:

First year

Second year

- Third year
- Fourth year
- Fifth year
- Sixth year

5. Skin phototype according to Fitzpatrick:

Supplementary Figure 1. Visual reference scale for the six Fitzpatrick skin phototypes.

Supplementary Figure 1. illustrates the six Fitzpatrick skin phototypes (I–VI), ranging from very fair skin to deeply pigmented skin. This figure was specifically developed as a visual aid within the study questionnaire to facilitate accurate self-identification by students. The image was synthetically generated using an Artificial Intelligence (AI) model and subsequently reviewed and validated by a board-certified dermatologist to ensure clinical accuracy and scientific integrity, confirming alignment with the functional and phenotypic characteristics of the Fitzpatrick scale. As an AI-generated work, this image is not subject to traditional copyright restrictions and is available for public, academic, and professional use.

- Type I
- Type II

- Type III
- Type IV
- Type V
- Type VI
- I do not know

6. How would you describe your skin type?

- Oily
- Dry
- Combination
- Normal
- Sensitive
- I do not know

Section 2. Knowledge About Photoprotection (7 items)

7. Do you know what sunscreen is?

- Yes
- Not sure
- No

Scoring: (0 = No; 0.5 = Not sure; 1 = Yes)

8. Do you know what photoprotection means?

- Yes
- No

Scoring: (0 = No; 1 = Yes)

9. Do you know the minimum recommended SPF for daily use?

- Yes
- Not sure
- No

Scoring: (0 = No; 0.5 = Not sure; 1 = Yes)

10. Which sunscreen do you consider good?

Open-ended response

Scoring: 1 point if the participant mentions at least one valid characteristic or a specific sunscreen product/brand/type; 0 points if the response is “I don’t know” or left blank.

11. Are you aware that some sunscreens may harm marine ecosystems?

Yes

No

Scoring: (0 = No; 1 = Yes)

12. Are you familiar with endogenous photoprotective mechanisms (e.g., melanin)?

Yes

No

Scoring: (0 = No; 1 = Yes)

Section 3. Attitudes Toward Photoprotection (6 items)

13. Do you consider that you have sufficient information about the risks of excessive sun exposure?

Yes

Limited

No

Scoring: (0 = No; 1 = Limited; 2 = Yes; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

14. How often do you read sunscreen ingredients?

Never

Sometimes

Always

Scoring: (0 = Never; 1 = Sometimes; 2 = Always; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

15. How often do you check the SPF before using sunscreen?

- Never
- Rarely
- Frequently
- Always

Scoring: (0 = Never; 1 = Rarely; 2 = Frequently; 3 = Always; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

16. What is your main motivation for using sunscreen?

- Skin cancer prevention
- Photoaging prevention
- Combined motivation
- Avoid sunburn
- Extend safe sun exposure time
- Previous sun damage

Scoring: (Skin cancer prevention = 2; Combined motivation = 1; Extend safe exposure = 0; Others = 1; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

17. What is the main factor (independent of SPF) that you consider when choosing a sunscreen?

- Price
- Natural ingredients
- Texture
- Brand
- All of the above
- I do not know

Scoring: (Natural ingredients = 1; Texture = 1; Brand = 0; Price = 0; All of the above = 1)

18. What is your preferred sunscreen formulation?

- Cream

- Gel
- Spray
- Other
- Indifferent

Scoring: (1 point for any answer except “Indifferent”; 0 if “Indifferent”)

Section 4. Photoprotection Practices (7 items)

19. Do you use sunscreen?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Always

Scoring: (0 = Never; 1 = Sometimes; 2 = Always; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

20. How often do you apply sunscreen during outdoor activities?

- Never
- Rarely
- Frequently
- Always

Scoring: (0 = Never; 1 = Rarely; 2 = Frequently; 3 = Always; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

21. At what age did you start using sunscreen?

- Numeric response
- I have never used sunscreen

Scoring: (0 = Never; 1 = >25 years; 2 = 18–25; 3 = 11–17; 4 = 5–10; 5 = <5 years; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

22. Does your family use sunscreen regularly?

- Yes, regularly

Occasionally / inconsistently

No

Scoring: (Yes = 2; Occasional = 1; No = 0; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

23. Do you use additional sun protection measures besides sunscreen?

None

At least one (hat, clothing, shade)

All of the above

Scoring: (All = 2; At least one = 1; None = 0; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

24. As a medical student, do you recommend sunscreen to family members, friends, or patients?

Never

Sometimes

Always

Scoring: (Never = 0; Sometimes = 1; Always = 2; subsequently normalized to 0–1)

25. What SPF do you usually use?

Less than 30 or do not use

30 or higher

Scoring: (Less than 30 = 0; 30 or higher = 1)

Section 5. Barriers to Implementation of Adequate Photoprotection Practices (2 items)

26. What is your main reason for non-adherence to sunscreen use or photoprotection?

Forgetfulness

Discomfort

Lack of knowledge about reapplication frequency

Other

(Descriptive; not scored)

27. What would help you use sunscreen or photoprotection more regularly?

- Reminders (apps/messages)
- Greater affordability
- More convenient formulations
- More information about sun-related risks
- More educational campaigns on social media
- Other

(Descriptive; not scored)

Supplementary material 3. Scoring and Normalization Procedure

Each item in the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) sections was assigned a predefined numerical score according to the response options described in the questionnaire.

For items with ordinal response categories (e.g., 0–2 or 0–3), higher values reflected greater knowledge, more favorable attitudes, or better photoprotection practices.

To standardize the contribution of items with different maximum scores, responses were normalized to a 0–1 scale by dividing the observed score by the maximum possible score for that item:

$$\text{Normalized score} = \frac{\text{Observed score}}{\text{Maximum possible score}}$$

For example, if an item had a maximum score of 4 and a participant obtained a score of 2, the normalized value was calculated as $2/4 = 0.50$.

Domain scores were calculated as the mean of normalized item scores within each KAP dimension.

Items in Section 5 (Barriers) were descriptive and were not included in the scoring system.

A detailed description of the scoring framework and normalization procedure is provided in Supplementary Table S1, while the complete variable dictionary used for statistical analysis in SPSS is presented in Supplementary Table S2. The univariate assessment of data completeness and outlier detection is presented in Supplementary Table S3, allowing readers to evaluate data integrity and distributional characteristics of the analyzed variables.

Supplementary Table S1. Scoring System and Normalization of the Survey Instrument

Item No.	Section	Item	Response Options	Raw Score	Normalized Score (0–1)	Notes
1	Sociodemographic	Age (years)	Numeric	Continuous	–	Descriptive only
2	Sociodemographic	Sex	Male / Female	–	–	Descriptive only
3	Sociodemographic	Place of origin	Open-ended	–	–	Standardized to department
4	Sociodemographic	Year of medical school	First–Sixth year	–	–	Descriptive only
5	Sociodemographic	Skin phototype according to Fitzpatrick	Type I–VI / I do not know	–	–	Descriptive only
6	Sociodemographic	Self-perceived skin type	How would you describe your skin type?	Oily / Dry / Combination / Normal / Sensitive / I do not know	–	Descriptive only
7	Knowledge	Do you know what sunscreen is?	No / Not sure / Yes	0 / 0.5 / 1	0–1	Not sure = 0.5
8	Knowledge	Do you know what photoprotection means?	No / Yes	0 / 1	0–1	Dichotomous
9	Knowledge	Do you know the minimum recommended SPF for daily use?	No / Not sure / Yes	0 / 0.5 / 1	0–1	Not sure = 0.5
10	Knowledge	Which sunscreen do you consider good?	Open-ended	0 / 1	0–1	1 point if ≥ 1 scientifically appropriate characteristic is mentioned (e.g., broad-spectrum, SPF ≥ 30 , water-resistant) or if a specific sunscreen product, brand, or type is named; 0 points if “I don’t know” or left blank.
11	Knowledge	Are you aware that some sunscreens may harm marine ecosystems?	No / Yes	0 / 1	0–1	Dichotomous

Item No.	Section	Item	Response Options	Raw Score	Normalized Score (0–1)	Notes
12	Knowledge	Are you familiar with endogenous photoprotective mechanisms (e.g., melanin)?	No / Yes	0 / 1	0–1	Dichotomous
13	Attitudes	Do you consider that you have sufficient information about the risks of excessive sun exposure?	No / Limited / Yes	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	Limited = 0.5
14	Attitudes	How often do you read sunscreen ingredients?	Never / Sometimes / Always	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	–
15	Attitudes	How often do you check the SPF before using sunscreen?	Never / Rarely / Frequently / Always	0 / 1 / 2 / 3	Raw ÷ 3	Ordinal normalization
16	Attitudes	What is your main motivation for using sunscreen?	Skin cancer prevention / Photoaging prevention / Combined motivation / Avoid sunburn / Extend safe sun exposure time / Previous sun damage	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	Skin cancer prevention = 2; Combined motivation = 2; Extend safe exposure = 0; other single motivations = 1
17	Attitudes	What is the main factor (independent of SPF) that you consider when choosing a sunscreen?	Price / Natural ingredients / Texture / Brand / All of the above / I do not know	0 / 1	0–1	Natural ingredients = 1; Texture = 1; All of the above = 1; Price, Brand or I do not know = 0
18	Attitudes	What is your preferred sunscreen formulation?	Cream / Gel / Spray / Other / Indifferent	1 / 0	0–1	Any except “Indifferent” = 1
19	Practices	Do you use sunscreen?	Never / Sometimes / Always	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	–
20	Practices	How often do you apply sunscreen during outdoor activities?	Never / Rarely / Frequently / Always	0 / 1 / 2 / 3	Raw ÷ 3	–

Item No.	Section	Item	Response Options	Raw Score	Normalized Score (0–1)	Notes
21	Practices	At what age did you start using sunscreen?	Never / >25 / 18–25 / 11–17 / 5–10 / <5 years	0–5	Raw ÷ 5	Categorical recoding
22	Practices	Does your family use sunscreen regularly?	No / Occasionally / Yes	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	–
23	Practices	Do you use additional sun protection measures besides sunscreen?	None / At least one / All of the above	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	–
24	Practices	As a medical student, do you recommend sunscreen to family members, friends, or patients?	Never / Sometimes / Always	0 / 1 / 2	Raw ÷ 2	–
25	Practices	What SPF do you usually use?	Less than 30 or do not use / 30 or higher	0 / 1	0–1	Dichotomous
26	Barriers	What is your main reason for non-adherence to sunscreen use or photoprotection?	Multiple choice	–	–	Descriptive only
27	Barriers	What would help you use sunscreen more regularly?	Multiple choice	–	–	Descriptive only

Supplementary Table 1. Scoring system and normalization procedure for the translated survey instrument. This table details the scoring criteria applied to each item of the questionnaire, including raw score assignment, normalization procedures (0–1 scale), and notes regarding recoding or classification rules. Sociodemographic variables were analyzed descriptively and not included in composite scores. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) items were scored according to predefined criteria and normalized to ensure comparability across domains. Barrier-related items were analyzed descriptively and were not included in the composite KAP score calculation.

Supplementary Table S2. Variable Dictionary for the Photoprotection KAP Dataset (SPSS Format)

Variable Name	Question (English)
ID	Participant identifier
Age	Age (years): Numeric response (in years)
Sex	Sex: Male / Female
Origin	Place of origin: Open-ended response (municipality/department; later standardized at the departmental level)
AcademicYear	Year of medical school: First year / Second year / Third year / Fourth year / Fifth year / Sixth year
SkinPhototype	Skin phototype according to the Fitzpatrick scale: Type I / Type II / Type III / Type IV / Type V / Type VI / I do not know
SkinSelfType	How would you describe your skin type? (Oily / Dry / Combination / Normal / Sensitive / I do not know)
KnowSunscreen	Do you know what sunscreen is? (Yes / Not sure / No)
KnowSunscreen_score	Normalized score for knowledge of sunscreen
KnowPhotoprotection	Do you know what photoprotection means? (Yes / No)
KnowPhotoprotection_score	Normalized score for photoprotection knowledge
KnowMinSPF	Do you know the minimum recommended SPF for daily use? (Yes / Not sure / No)
KnowMinSPF_score	Normalized score for minimum recommended SPF knowledge
GoodSunscreen	Which sunscreen do you consider good? (Open-ended response)
GoodSunscreen_score	Score for correct identification of at least one valid sunscreen characteristic
KnowMarineImpact	Are you aware that some sunscreens may harm marine ecosystems? (Yes / No)
KnowMarineImpact_score	Normalized score for awareness of marine ecosystem impact
KnowEndogenousProtection	Are you familiar with endogenous photoprotective mechanisms (e.g., melanin)? (Yes / No)
KnowEndogenousProtection_score	Normalized score for endogenous photoprotection knowledge
SufficientInfo	Do you consider that you have sufficient information about the risks of excessive sun exposure? (Yes / Limited / No)
SufficientInfo_score	Normalized score for perceived sufficiency of information
ReadIngredients	How often do you read sunscreen ingredients? (Never / Sometimes / Always)
ReadIngredients_score	Normalized score for reading sunscreen ingredients
CheckSPF	How often do you check the SPF before using sunscreen? (Never / Rarely / Frequently / Always)
CheckSPF_score	Normalized score for checking SPF
MainMotivation	What is your main motivation for using sunscreen?
MainMotivation_quant	Quantitative score for main motivation (0–2)
MainMotivation_score	Normalized main motivation score

Variable Name	Question (English)
SunscreenFactors	Main factor considered when choosing a sunscreen (independent of SPF): Price / Natural ingredients / Texture / Brand / All of the above / I do not know
SunscreenFactors_score	Score for sunscreen selection factors
PreferredFormulation	What is your preferred sunscreen formulation? (Cream / Gel / Spray / Other / Indifferent)
PreferredFormulation_score	Normalized score for sunscreen formulation preference
UseSunscreen	Do you use sunscreen? (Never / Sometimes / Always)
UseSunscreen_score	Normalized sunscreen use score
SunscreenFrequency	How often do you apply sunscreen during outdoor activities? (Never / Rarely / Frequently / Always)
SunscreenFrequency_score	Normalized sunscreen application frequency
AgeStartSunscreen	At what age did you start using sunscreen? (Numeric response / Never used)
AgeStartSunscreen_cat	Categorized age of sunscreen initiation (Never, >25, 18–25, 11–17, 5–10, <5 years)
AgeStartSunscreen_score	Normalized score for age of sunscreen initiation
FamilyUseSunscreen	Does your family use sunscreen regularly? (Yes / Occasionally / No)
FamilyUseSunscreen_score	Normalized family sunscreen use score
OtherProtection	Do you use additional sun protection measures besides sunscreen? (None / At least one / All of the above)
OtherProtection_score	Normalized score for additional photoprotection measures
RecommendSunscreen	As a medical student, do you recommend sunscreen to family members, friends, or patients? (Never / Sometimes / Always)
RecommendSunscreen_score	Normalized sunscreen recommendation score
SPFUsed	What SPF do you usually use? (Less than 30 or do not use / 30 or higher)
SPFUsed_score	Score for usual SPF use
TotalKnowledge	Total normalized Knowledge score
TotalAttitudes	Total normalized Attitudes score
TotalPractices	Total normalized Practices score
TotalKAP	Overall Knowledge–Attitudes–Practices (KAP) score

Supplementary Table S2. Variable Dictionary for the Photoprotection KAP Dataset (SPSS Format). This table presents the complete variable dictionary used for dataset construction and statistical analysis in SPSS. It includes variable names, corresponding survey items (English version), and conceptual definitions to ensure transparency and reproducibility of data processing and scoring procedures. Derived variables include normalized scores (0–1) for individual items and aggregated domain scores (Knowledge, Attitudes, Practices), as well as the overall KAP score. All variable codifications are fully aligned with the translated survey instrument (Supplementary Material 2) and the methodological description provided in Supplementary Material 3. **Data Availability:** The full anonymized dataset is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18530433>. This dataset is also part of the academic thesis entitled: “Actitudes, conocimientos y prácticas de fotoprotección en alumnos de la facultad de ciencias medicas de UNICIT del periodo comprendido en el mes de Mayo del año 2025”

Supplementary Table S3. Univariate analysis of data completeness and outlier detection (N = 133)

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Missing (n)	Missing (%)	Outliers (Low)	Outliers (High)
ID	133	67.00	38.538	0	0.0	0	0
Age	133	19.50	1.893	0	0.0	0	1
KnowSunscreen_score	133	0.981	0.1136	0	0.0	–	–
KnowPhotoprotection_score	133	0.6090	0.48981	0	0.0	0	0
KnowMinSPF_score	133	0.4586	0.43102	0	0.0	0	0
GoodSunscreen_score	133	0.8797	0.32654	0	0.0	–	–
KnowMarineImpact_score	133	0.3008	0.46032	0	0.0	0	0
KnowEndogenousSunscreens_score	133	0.2180	0.41448	0	0.0	–	–
SufficientInfo_score	133	0.6203	0.31473	0	0.0	0	0
ReadIngredients_score	133	0.5000	0.37437	0	0.0	0	0
CheckSPF_score	133	0.5539	0.35269	0	0.0	0	0
MainMotivation_score	133	0.7444	0.25832	0	0.0	0	0
SunscreensFactors_score	133	0.6842	0.46659	0	0.0	0	0
PreferredFormulation_score	133	0.8346	0.37296	0	0.0	–	–
UseSunscreen_score	133	0.571	0.3948	0	0.0	0	0
SPFUsed_score	133	0.86	0.343	0	0.0	–	–
OutdoorActivity_score	133	0.5689	0.29809	0	0.0	0	0
AgeStartSunscreen	117	14.79	3.782	16	12.0	6	0
AgeStartSunscreen_score	133	0.5098	0.22759	0	0.0	16	3
FamilyUseSunscreen_score	133	0.594	0.4358	0	0.0	0	0
SunscreensFrequency_score	133	0.4787	0.2431	0	0.0	0	0
OtherProtection_score	133	0.526	0.3275	0	0.0	–	–
RecommendSunscreen_score	133	0.929	0.2231	0	0.0	–	–
TotalKnowledge	133	3.4474	1.13695	0	0.0	0	0
TotalAttitudes	133	3.9373	1.00454	0	0.0	2	0
TotalPractices	133	5.0424	1.24089	0	0.0	3	0
TotalKAP	133	12.4271	2.52202	0	0.0	1	1

Supplementary Table S3. Univariate analysis of data completeness and outlier detection. Summary statistics for all study variables (N = 133) are presented, including mean, standard deviation (SD), frequency of missing values, and number of extreme values. Outliers were identified using the interquartile range (IQR) method, defined as cases falling outside the interval (Q1 – 1.5×IQR, Q3 + 1.5×IQR). Overall data completeness was high, with the exception of *AgeStartSunscreen*, which presented 12% missing values.

Supplementary Material 5. Assessment of Normality and Homogeneity of Variances

Normality Assessment

The normality of continuous quantitative variables was evaluated in the total sample only, including: Age, Age at Start of Sunscreen Use, Total Knowledge Score, Total Attitudes Score, Total Practices Score, and Total KAP Score. Normality tests were conducted using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction, considering the sample size ($N > 50$), and visually inspected using histograms and Q–Q plots. The results are summarized in Supplementary Table S4, while graphical inspections of normality are provided in Figures S2–S4.

Supplementary Table S4. Normality Test of Continuous Quantitative Variables (Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test)

Variable	N	Std. Deviation	Test	Sig.	Decision
Age	133	1.893	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors, Monte Carlo)	< .001	Reject the null hypothesis
Total Knowledges	133	1.247	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors, Monte Carlo)	< .001	Reject the null hypothesis
Total Attitudes	133	1.005	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors, Monte Carlo)	.003	Reject the null hypothesis
Total Practices	133	1.241	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors, Monte Carlo)	.089	Retain the null hypothesis
Total KAP	133	2.641	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors, Monte Carlo)	.293	Retain the null hypothesis
Age Start Sunscreen	117	0.228	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors, Monte Carlo)	< .001	Reject the null hypothesis

Supplementary Table S4. Univariate normality test for continuous variables using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction and Monte Carlo simulation (10,000 samples). N represents the number of valid observations per variable. Significance values (Sig.) ≥ 0.05 indicate that the variable meets the assumption of normality, whereas $p < 0.05$ indicates significant deviation from normality. These results informed the selection of parametric or non-parametric tests for subsequent comparative analyses.

Supplementary Figure S2. Visual assessment of normality for Age and Age of Sunscreen Initiation

Supplementary Figure S2. Normal and Detrended Q-Q Plots for age-related variables. The figure illustrates the distribution of observed data compared to a theoretical normal distribution. **(A)** Normal Q-Q plot for participant age, showing a linear trend. **(B)** Detrended Q-Q plot for age, where points are distributed around the central line without prominent systematic patterns. Despite the visual proximity to normality in A and B, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($p < .001$) indicates a significant deviation from a Gaussian distribution. **(C)** Normal Q-Q plot for the age of sunscreen initiation, displaying systematic deviations from the diagonal line, particularly at the distribution tails. **(D)** Detrended Q-Q plot for the age of sunscreen initiation, revealing a distinct parabolic arc pattern. This systematic configuration confirms high skewness and kurtosis, consistent with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov result ($p < .001$), justifying the use of non-parametric methods for these variables.

Supplementary Figure S3. Visual assessment of normality for Total Attitudes and Total Knowledges scores.

Supplementary Figure S3. This figure illustrates the distribution of observed scores relative to a theoretical normal distribution. (A) Normal Q-Q plot for Total Attitudes; while scores follow a linear trend, the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($p = .003$) confirms a significant deviation from normality. (B) Detrended Q-Q plot for Total Attitudes; the concave residual pattern indicates systematic deviations in skewness and kurtosis. (C) Normal Q-Q plot for Total Knowledges; the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($p < .001$) indicates significant non-normality, largely attributed to the discrete nature of the measurement scale. (D) Detrended Q-Q plot for Total Knowledges; the ascending linear trajectory of residuals confirms a systematic departure from a Gaussian distribution. As summarized in Supplementary Table S4, these distributions necessitated the use of non-parametric statistical methods for these specific variables.

Supplementary Figure S4. Visual assessment of normality for Total KAP and Total Practices scores.

Supplementary Figure S3. This figure illustrates the distribution of scores for dimensions where the null hypothesis of normality was retained. (A) Normal Q-Q plot for Total KAP score; data points show a robust fit to the expected normality diagonal, justifying the use of parametric inferential statistics for correlation and mean comparison analyses. (B) Detrended Q-Q plot for Total KAP; residuals exhibit a primarily random dispersion near the central horizontal line, supporting the Kolmogorov-Smirnov result ($p = .293$). The points in the lower-left quadrant represent moderate outliers with deviations near -1.0. (C) Normal Q-Q plot for the Practices dimension (Total Practices); observed scores align consistently with the theoretical trend line despite minor dispersions at the distribution extremes. (D) Detrended Q-Q plot for the Practices dimension; although a slight non-linear trend is visible, most observations remain within an acceptable deviation range (absolute value < 0.6), which does not compromise the global statistical normality validated by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($p = .089$).

In brief, Total KAP and Total Practices scores met the normality assumption, whereas Total Knowledge and Total Attitudes scores deviated from normality. These findings guided the selection of parametric or non-parametric tests in subsequent comparative analyses.

Homogeneity of Variances Assessment

For comparative analyses involving continuous variables across independent groups, homogeneity of variances was evaluated using Levene's test. Most variables exhibited homogeneous variances; however, some, including Age at Start of Sunscreen Use and Total KAP, showed variance heterogeneity in certain groups. Detailed results are presented in Supplementary Table S4.

Supplementary Table S4. Homogeneity of Variances Assessed for Continuous Variables Across Comparison Groups

Variable	Group Compared	Levene Statistic	Sig.	Homogeneous?
Total Knowledges	Sex	0.006	0.937	Yes
Total Attitudes	Sex	0.075	0.784	Yes
Total Practices	Sex	1.990	0.161	Yes
Total KAP	Sex	0.497	0.914	Yes
Age Start Sunscreen	Sex	4.157	0.044	No
Age	Sex	1.728	0.191	Yes
Total Knowledges	Academic year	2.311	0.061	Yes
Total Attitudes	Academic year	0.262	0.902	Yes
Total Practices	Academic year	0.731	0.573	Yes
Total KAP	Academic year	1.225	0.303	Yes
Age Start Sunscreen	Academic year	3.623	0.008	No
Age	Academic year	0.789	0.534	Yes
Total Knowledges	Skin phototypes	1.508	0.192	Yes
Total Attitudes	Skin phototypes	0.484	0.788	Yes
Total Practices	Skin phototypes	2.207	0.058	Yes
Total KAP	Skin phototypes	3.361	0.007	No
Age Start Sunscreen	Skin phototypes	1.306	0.267	Yes
Age	Skin phototypes	1.688	0.142	Yes
Total Practices	SPF Used	1.336	0.250	Yes
Total KAP	Recommend Sunscreen	0.329	0.720	Yes
Total Practices	Used Sunscreen	5.555	0.005	No

Supplementary Table S4. Homogeneity of variance assessed using Levene's test for continuous variables across comparison groups. The test evaluates whether the variance of a quantitative variable is equal between groups, a key assumption for parametric tests such as Student's t-test and ANOVA. The table shows results based on the mean ("Based on Mean"), the standard approach widely used in the literature. "Levene Statistic" presents the F value calculated from group means, "Sig." indicates the p-value of the test, and "Homogeneous?" summarizes whether the assumption of homogeneity of variances is met (Yes = $p \geq 0.05$; No = $p < 0.05$). Most variables exhibit homogeneous variances; exceptions, such as Age Start Sunscreen and Total KAP in specific groups, require adjusted parametric tests or non-parametric alternatives.

Levene's test results were based on group means ("Based on Mean"), which is standard practice in the literature when data do not exhibit extreme values or marked skewness. The table reports the F statistic (Levene Statistic), p-values (Sig.), and an interpretation column (Homogeneous?) indicating whether the assumption was met. Variables violating homogeneity assumptions were analyzed using adjusted parametric tests (e.g., Brown-Forsythe ANOVA) or equivalent non-parametric tests.

Supplementary material 6. Exploratory Associations Between Individual Photoprotection Behaviors and Composite Scores

Supplementary Material S6 presents exploratory analyses conducted to examine the internal consistency and plausibility of the ad hoc KAP scoring system.

Because the survey instrument was specifically developed for this study and did not undergo formal psychometric validation, additional bivariate analyses were performed to evaluate whether individual photoprotection behaviors that contributed to the composite scores (Total Practice and global KAP) showed coherent and graded associations with their corresponding aggregate measures.

These analyses were conducted exclusively for methodological transparency and internal consistency assessment. Given that the examined behaviors are components of the composite scores, the results are presented separately in the Supplementary Materials to avoid analytical circularity in the primary inferential findings (Table S5). The corresponding distributions are illustrated in Supplementary Figure S5, which graphically depicts the graded relationship between individual behaviors and composite scores.

Supplementary Table S5. Exploratory Associations Between Individual Photoprotection Behaviors and Composite Scores

Variable / Factor	Dependent Variable	Test	Statistic	df	p-value	Post Hoc
Frequency of Sunscreen Use (Never / Sometimes / Always)	Total Practice Score	One-way ANOVA†	F = 54.84	2,130	<0.001	Games–Howell: Always > Sometimes > Never*
Typical SPF Used (<30 or none vs. ≥30)	Total Practice Score	Student’s t-test	t = -7.17	131	<0.001	≥30 > <30 / none
Sunscreen Recommendation (Never / Sometimes / Always)	Total KAP Score	One-way ANOVA	F = 15.758	2	<0.001	Bonferroni: Always > Never and Sometimes*

Supplementary Table S5. Exploratory associations between individual photoprotection behaviors and composite scores. This table presents bivariate associations between specific behaviors included in the scoring algorithm and the corresponding composite domain scores (Total Practice and global KAP). Given that these behaviors contribute directly to the construction of the composite variables, these analyses were conducted exclusively for internal consistency and plausibility assessment of the ad hoc instrument and are presented separately to avoid analytical circularity in the primary inferential results. †ANOVA significance was confirmed using the Brown–Forsythe robust test when variance homogeneity assumptions were not met. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Supplementary Figure S5. Impact of specific photoprotection practices on KAP scores.

Figure S5. The left panel displays the distribution of total Practice scores according to the frequency of sunscreen use (Always, Sometimes, Never), demonstrating a significant graded relationship where more frequent use correlates with higher Practice scores ($p < 0.001$). The center panel presents a dot plot distribution of global KAP scores categorized by the frequency of sunscreen recommendation (Always, Sometimes, Never), showing higher concentrations of top-tier scores among those who consistently recommend its use. The right panel illustrates the mean of total KAP scores according to recommendation frequency, where the upward linear trend highlights that consistent recommendation is associated with significantly higher overall KAP scores ($p < 0.001$).

Supplementary material 7. Additional Methodology: Systematic Literature Review to Contextualize Study Novelty

Objective

To rigorously contextualize the present study within the global scientific literature and to substantiate its regional novelty, a systematic literature review was conducted to identify prior studies assessing Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) related to photoprotection among medical students in Central America and the Caribbean.

Search Strategy

The search was conducted on February 8, 2026, across six bibliographic sources to ensure comprehensive coverage of international and regional scientific literature. The databases consulted were PubMed/MEDLINE, SciELO, Dialnet, the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), and Google Scholar, which was searched separately using English and Spanish search strategies.

Database-specific search equations were constructed using combinations of controlled vocabulary and free-text terms in English and Spanish referring to knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP/CAP), photoprotection and related concepts (sun protection, sunscreen, sun exposure, ultraviolet radiation), and medical students. In PubMed, an additional geographic filter was incorporated, explicitly including the names of all Central American and Caribbean countries.

The geographically restricted PubMed search yielded zero results. Searches in SciELO, Dialnet, DOAJ, and Google Scholar identified a total of 22 records. The complete search strings, database outputs are listed in supplementary table S6.

Supplementary Table S6. Search Strategy and Results of the Systematic Literature Review (February 8, 2026)

Database	Date of Search	Search Strategy	Results (n)
PubMed/MEDLINE	February 8, 2026	((knowledge[Title/Abstract] OR attitude*[Title/Abstract] OR practice*[Title/Abstract] OR KAP[Title/Abstract]) AND ("sun protection"[Title/Abstract] OR photoprotection[Title/Abstract] OR sunscreen[Title/Abstract] OR "sun exposure"[Title/Abstract] OR "ultraviolet radiation"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("medical student*[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Central America" OR "Caribbean" OR Belize OR "Costa Rica" OR "El Salvador" OR Guatemala OR Honduras OR Nicaragua OR Panama OR Cuba OR "Dominican Republic" OR Haiti OR "Puerto Rico" OR Jamaica OR Barbados OR "Trinidad Tobago"))	0
SciELO	February 8, 2026	(conocimiento* OR actitud* OR práctica* OR KAP OR knowledge OR attitudes OR practices) AND ("fotoprotección" OR "protección solar" OR photoprotection OR "sun protection") AND ("estudiantes de medicina" OR "medical students")	1
Dialnet	February 8, 2026	("estudiantes de medicina") AND ("fotoprotección" OR "protección solar") AND (conocimiento* OR actitud* OR práctica* OR KAP)	2
DOAJ	February 8, 2026	"medical students" "sun protection" knowledge	5
Google Scholar (English)	February 8, 2026	allintitle: "medical students" ("sun protection" OR photoprotection) (knowledge OR attitudes OR practices)	10
Google Scholar (Spanish)	February 8, 2026	allintitle: "estudiantes de medicina" ("protección solar" OR fotoprotección) (conocimiento OR actitudes OR prácticas)	4
Total			22

Supplementary Table S6. Detailed search strategy and database results for the systematic literature review. This table summarizes the bibliographic databases consulted, date of search (February 8, 2026), database-specific search strings, and number of records retrieved during the systematic literature review conducted to identify studies evaluating knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to photoprotection among medical students. The geographically restricted PubMed search yielded zero results for Central America and the Caribbean.

Eligibility Criteria

Studies were eligible for inclusion if they were primary research articles or academic theses evaluating knowledge, attitudes, and/or practices related to photoprotection in medical students. Studies conducted in non-medical student populations, review articles, editorials, opinion papers, and studies not assessing KAP constructs were excluded.

Study Selection Process

A three-phase screening process was implemented.

In the identification and deduplication phase, the initial search retrieved 22 records. All references were imported into a spreadsheet and examined for duplication using DOI, title, and author comparisons. Three exact duplicates were identified and removed, including one article from *Dermatology Practical & Conceptual*, one article from the *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*, and one Peruvian thesis. Nineteen unique records remained after deduplication.

During the title and abstract screening phase, the 19 remaining records were independently assessed for relevance. One study was excluded because it was a systematic review without primary population data (Wilkerson et al., 2018). Eighteen records proceeded to full-text evaluation.

In the full-text review phase, all 18 studies met the predefined inclusion criteria. The final analytical step consisted of geographic classification of the country or region where each study population was located.

The complete study selection process is illustrated in Supplementary Figure S6 (PRISMA flow diagram).

Supplementary Figure S6. PRISMA flow diagram of the study selection process.

Supplementary Figure S6. PRISMA flow diagram of the study selection process. The flowchart delineates the stages of identification, screening, and inclusion of studies for the review. A total of 8 records were initially identified through database searching (Dialnet, \$n=2\$; Scielo, \$n=1\$; DOAJ, \$n=5\$), while 0 records were found in Pubmed/Medline. After removing 3 duplicate records, 19 records were screened, leading to 18 reports assessed for eligibility. Ultimately, 18 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final review.

Geographic Mapping of Included Studies

A total of 18 primary studies were confirmed, comprising 14 peer-reviewed journal articles and 4 academic theses. Seven studies were conducted in South America, including five from Peru, one from Brazil, and one from Ecuador. Eight studies originated from Europe, including four from Turkey, two conducted in Spain and Italy (one study including both countries), one from Poland, and one from Albania. Two studies were conducted in Asia, one in Vietnam and one in India. Two studies originated from North America, one from the United States and one from Mexico. One study was conducted in Africa, specifically in Nigeria (Table S7).

Supplementary Table S7. Geographic Distribution and Characteristics of Included Studies on Photoprotection KAP in Medical Students (n = 18)

No.	First Author (Year)	Country	Region	Study Type	Source / Journal	DOI / URL
1	(Chavez et al., 2025)	Peru	South America	Journal Article	Journal of Preventive Medicine and Hygiene	10.15167/2421-4248/jpmh2025.66.3.3543
2	(Aliaga-Echevarría & Soto-Cáceres, 2018)	Peru	South America	Journal Article	Revista Experimental de Medicina	https://rem.hrlamb.gob.pe/index.php/REM/article/view/141
3	(Diaz et al., 2020)	Peru	South America	Thesis	Universidad Peruana Cayetano Heredia	https://repositorio.upch.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12866/16430
4	(Trelles Tijero & Vaughan Poggi, 2023)	Peru	South America	Thesis	Universidad San Martín de Porres	https://repositorio.usmp.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12727/11767
5	(Santillan Calderón & Tenelema Alcocer, 2022)	Ecuador	South America	Thesis	Universidad Nacional de Chimborazo	http://dspace.unach.edu.ec/handle/51000/9987
6	(Malta-Purim & Wroblevski, 2014)	Brazil	South America	Journal Article	Revista Brasileira de Educação Médica	http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0100-55022014000400009
7	(Rodríguez-Zamorano et al., 2018)	Spain	Europe	Journal Article	Semergen	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semerg.2018.02.004
8	(Durán-Ávila et al., 2025)	Spain & Italy	Europe	Journal Article	Actas Dermo-Sifiliográficas	10.1016/j.ad.2024.12.002
9	(Bilushi et al., 2012)	Albania	Europe	Journal Article	European Medical, Health and Pharmaceutical Journal	10.12955/emhpj.v4i0.355
10	(Agata Glac et al., 2023)	Poland	Europe	Journal Article	Journal of Education, Health and Sport	10.12775/JEHS.2023.14.01.012
11	(Hızlı et al., 2025)	Turkey	Europe	Journal Article	Balıkesir Medical Journal	https://doi.org/10.33716/bmedj.1709188

No.	First Author (Year)	Country	Region	Study Type	Source / Journal	DOI / URL
12	(Güner Karaca & Ateş, 2025)	Turkey	Europe	Journal Article	Konuralp Medical Journal	https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ktd/article/1690477
13	(Emre Guven et al., 2025)	Turkey	Europe	Journal Article	Dermatology Practical & Conceptual	10.5826/dpc.1502a4996
14	(Ha et al., 2025)	Vietnam	Asia	Journal Article	Materia Socio-Medica	10.5455/msm.2025.37.136-143
15	(Priya Prem et al., 2020)	India	Asia	Journal Article	Turkderm	10.4274/turkderm.galenos.2020.38455
16	(Hymowitz et al., 2006)	United States	North America	Journal Article	Archives of Dermatology	10.1001/archderm.142.4.523
17	(Ramos et al., 2016)	Mexico	North America	Journal Article	Dermatología Cosmética, Médica y Quirúrgica	https://www.medigraphic.com/cgi-bin/new/resumenI.cgi?IDARTICULO=65920
18	(Erere Otofrowei & Uchechi G Ezem, 2024)	Nigeria	Africa	Journal Article	Journal of Clinical Sciences	10.4103/jcls.jcls_103_23

Supplementary Table S6. Geographic distribution and bibliographic characteristics of included studies. This table summarizes the 18 primary studies identified through the exploratory literature search on knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding photoprotection among medical students. Fourteen were peer-reviewed journal articles and four were academic theses. Studies were geographically distributed across South America (n = 7), Europe (n = 8), Asia (n = 2), North America (n = 2), and Africa (n = 1). No eligible studies were identified from Central America or the Caribbean, confirming a regional evidence gap.

Conclusion: Justification of Study Novelty

This systematic literature review demonstrates a clear and significant geographic gap in the scientific literature. Although multiple global regions, including South America, Europe, Asia, North America, and Africa, have published research evaluating photoprotection-related KAP among medical students, no evidence was identified from Central America or the Caribbean.

To the best available knowledge as of February 2026, the present study represents the first investigation of this type conducted in this region, specifically in Nicaragua. This regional novelty strengthens the scientific relevance of the study and contributes new data from a tropical, middle-income context that has been underrepresented in dermatological and public health research. The findings provide an essential baseline for the development of culturally and regionally appropriate educational and public health strategies in Central America and the Caribbean.

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